

**PSYCHOLINGUISTICS, LANGUAGE ACQUISITION THROUGH
TRANSLATION**

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Annotation: *Actuality of this article is that it is directed to define and characterize the role of psycholinguistic aspects in the process of teaching English, which simultaneously influences the acquired knowledge and the process of its implementation in real life. In addition, though the department of psycholinguistics is considered one of the youngest branches of linguistics, it is significantly important in the educational process, for acquiring new language.*

Key words: *psycholinguistics, language production, language acquisition through translating*

Currently, the educational reforms implemented in Uzbekistan are aimed at creating decent living conditions for people. In accordance with PQ-5117 dated 19.05.2021, the decision "On measures to bring the popularization of foreign language learning to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was approved, and teaching foreign languages is a priority of the educational policy development as a direction, to fundamentally improve the quality of education in this direction, to attract qualified pedagogues to the field, and to increase the

population's interest in learning foreign languages. President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev's review of the changes taking place in our country highlighted the fact that education has become one of the areas where the most investments are made, and that every year about 35% the state budget is allocated to the education sector.

In addition, incentives are being created for younger generation in almost all directions to learn a second foreign language in depth. For example, a student can learn English grammar easily, increase vocabulary, understand and analyze other skills faster with various methods used in education. A bright example of this is the development of psycholinguistics in language learning. Hence, psycholinguistics has presented many theories that explain how a person acquires language, develops and comprehends spoken and written not only own language, but also second language.

Language production refers to the way people produce language in written or spoken form in a way that conveys intelligible meanings to others. One of the most effective ways to explain the way people express meaning using rule-driven languages is to observe and analyze examples. speech errors, which include incorrect beginnings of words, repetitions, rearrangements and constant pauses between words or sentences, as well as language slips, analogies, substitutions, exchanges.

According to the combination of psycholinguistics, there are psychology, which deals with individuals' mind and behavior, and linguistics, which studies the language itself. Overall, in general, psycholinguistics can be described as a science that studies mind and language. It is related to the relationship between the human mind and language, as it studies the processes that take place in the brain in the production and perception of language. As it was mentioned in Norita Purba's work that psycholinguistics encompasses three main ideas: language production, language comprehension, and language acquisition.

Language production refers to the processes involved in creating and expressing meaning through language. Language comprehension refers to the processes involved in interpreting and understanding written and spoken language. Language acquisition refers to the processes of mastering a mother tongue or a second language. Psycholinguistics has presented many theories that explain the above three points. Theories have been very useful in language teaching. Some experts use them as basic theories in the development of language teaching methods[1].

In turn, psychologists are once again interested in the role of linguistic structures in language processing. Some argue that at the moment Psycholinguistics has switched to an active style since the 1960s. The interaction of language structure and language processing may be the main subject of psycholinguistic research, but this interaction is now subject to the dual and equally important rigor of linguistic analysis and psychological experimentation. Although psychology and linguistics are once again equal partners in a psycholinguistic enterprise, they do not always agree with the same philosophy of science. One of the current questions is the modular or interactivity of the language processing system, and recent research examines the degree of modularity or interaction in the system. Linguists generally favored the modular hypothesis, while psychologists were more attracted to interactive explanations of the principles of language and learning [2].

Language comprehension is an important aspect of daily activities for people of all ages. Comprehension of written and oral language is based on the ability to correctly process word and phrase meanings, sentence grammar, speech or text structure. Difficulties in any of these areas can lead to comprehension problems. Age-related memory decline has been compared in many studies by young and older adults in language comprehension tasks.

The initial focus of psycholinguistics was in the philosophical and educational fields, mainly because it was located in departments other than the applied sciences

(for example, holistic information about how the human brain works). Contemporary research uses biology, neuroscience, cognitive science, linguistics, and information science to study how the mind-brain works with language and lesser-known processes in the social sciences, human development, communication theories, and infant development, among others. Psycholinguistics uses theoretical and empirical methods related to psychology and linguistics to analyze the thought processes that determine the basis of language learning and use.

The latest and most relevant period in psycholinguistics coincides with the development of cognitive science as an interdisciplinary field. Psycholinguistics is now concerned with a broader field of study, namely the nature of knowledge, the structure of mental representations and how they are used in mental processes such as reasoning and decision making. Current psycholinguistic theory reflects considerable theoretical diversity in both psychology and linguistics, but there is nevertheless considerable interdisciplinary activity. More researchers than ever are aware of developments in neighboring fields, demonstrating research goals and a breadth of knowledge that is not limited to a single discipline. Linguists and psychologists can no longer ignore scientific answers from other fields that affect research problems in their field and the explanations they offer for them.

At present, there are various discussions about the role of innate ability in language acquisition. The influence of transformational grammar, recent research in ecology, and developmental analysis of acquisition and learning have all fueled psychologists' interest in innate aspects of mental development. Underlying every scientific debate in this regard is the explanation of human language acquisition. A characteristic feature of contemporary theories and research in this area is that they seek to establish the universality of this process, and postulate the existence of biological principles that determine the basis of universality. Theories have been used in language teaching. Some experts use them as basic theories in the

development of language teaching methods. This is known as the psycholinguistic approach.

Psycholinguistics has provided many theories that explain how humans acquire language, produce and perceive spoken and written language. Theories have been applied in the field of language teaching. Some experts use them as basic theories in the development of language teaching methods. This is known as the psycholinguistic approach. The psycholinguistic approach views learning as a cognitive individual process that takes place within the individual and then moves into the social dimension. As an approach, there are some methods developed based on the theories of psycholinguistics: the natural method, the general physical response method, and the suggestive method. These methods apply psycholinguistic principles: learning one's mother tongue or first language (first language acquisition), a second or third language (second language learning), language perception (language perception), and language (Language production). Language comprehension refers to listening and reading, while language production refers to speaking and writing. learning.

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